

Temporal and Spatial Dynamics of Heatwave-Wildfire Relationships over Africa

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1. Introduction

The dynamics of heatwaves and wildfires in Africa have been shaped by both natural and anthropogenic factors over millennia (Padin et al., 2024; Strydom & Savage, 2016; Justino et al., 2013). Historically, fires were rare in the dense tropical forests of West and Central Africa due to the high moisture content and rapid decomposition rates, which limited fuel availability. However, the increasing frequency of wildfires in these regions can now be attributed to rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, and forest degradation (Wimberly et al., 2024).

In the past century, the incidence of heatwaves in Africa has received relatively little attention compared to other regions. For instance, only two heatwaves in sub-Saharan Africa have been recorded in the Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT) over the past 120 years, whereas Europe has documented 83 heatwaves in the last four decades (Oxford University, 2020). This discrepancy highlights a significant research gap regarding the historical prevalence and impacts of heatwaves across the African continent.

Climate change is expected to exacerbate these trends, with projections indicating a marked increase in the frequency and intensity of heatwaves. Understanding the historical context of heatwaves and wildfires in Africa is crucial for developing effective climate adaptation strategies and mitigating the impacts of these extreme weather events on vulnerable ecosystems and communities.

While the relationship between heatwaves and wildfires is globally relevant, its effects can vary significantly by region. In Africa, for example, the geographic and climatic diversity means that certain areas may experience more pronounced impacts due to local conditions, such as land use and vegetation types (Ngoungue Langue et al., 2023; Kapwata et al., 2022). The complex interplay between drought, heatwaves, and local ecology means that some regions may become increasingly susceptible to wildfires, while others may not experience the same level of impact (Geneva Environment Network, 2022). Understanding this interrelationship is essential for developing effective strategies for wildfire management and mitigation, especially in regions where climate change is expected to exacerbate existing vulnerabilities.

1.2 Research Question

This study seeks to answer the question: do long-term changes in heat waves frequency modulate wildfire risks in tropical Africa?

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Study Area and Time Frame

Our study focuses on two fire hotspot regions in tropical Africa, located just north and south of the equator (Fig. A2). These regions were chosen due to their high levels of fire activity within the African tropics. The temporal extent of our dataset spans from 2003 to 2019, as fire activity data from MODIS is consistent during this period. Further details are available in appendix A2.

The occurrence of fire events is contingent upon the fulfillment of specific preconditions. Adequate availability of combustible materials is a primary requirement, coupled with environmental factors conducive to sustained combustion following ignition (Wimberly et al., 2024). We identify the fire seasons based on fire count data, which indicate the periods when environmental conditions are most favorable for fire ignition and spread. In the northern region, the fire season typically runs from November to April, while in the southern region, it occurs from May to October (Fig. 1a).

2.2 Data Sources

To ensure ease of access and consistency, we use ERA5 reanalysis data (Muñoz Sabater, 2019). Specifically, hourly 2-meter temperature was used to calculate heat waves, which we defined as periods of at least three consecutive days where the daily maximum 2-meter temperature exceeds the 90th percentile. We also use 2-meter temperature and dew point temperature to calculate vapor pressure deficit (VPD), following the method described by Dee et al. (2011). Additionally, we include annual CCI v2.7 land cover data (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2019).

To identify dry conditions, we use the Global Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) database (Beguería et al., 2014). For fire data, we use NASA's Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) active fire data (NASA FIRMS, 2020) and the MODIS FireCCI 5.1 dataset (Lizundia-Loiola et al., 2020). All data is processed and spatially aligned to the 0.25-degree ERA5 grid. For further details, see Appendix A1.

2.3 Analytical Methods

To get an insight into the large-scale dynamics of fire activity and heatwave occurrence at longer timescales, we aggregate data over the study areas to create annual time series and linear trends.

Additionally, for each grid cell in the study areas, we calculate monthly time series of the heatwave and fire metrics. We then calculate the Spearman's rank coefficient for those variable pairs we want to test for correlation.

Further we calculate the rate of information flow after Liang, X. S. (2014) to test for a potential causal relationship between heatwave and fire metrics. This is also done for each monthly time series calculated for each grid cell.

We calculate both the Spearman coefficient and information flow for the full monthly time series and for time series with only the months that are inside the fire season. Because of the closeness to the equator of the study areas, spatial averages are calculated without latitudinal weighting.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Key Findings

Over the study period (2003–2019), our analysis of fire activity and associated climatic indices across tropical Africa reveal contrasting regional dynamics despite an overall increase in extreme heat events. Notably, while the frequency of heatwaves increased significantly (Fig. 1d), both fire count and burned area declined across our areas of interest (Figs. 1e, 1f).

Figure 1 (a) Total number of fires for each area (Northern area in blue and Southern in gold). Long term per calendar month; (b) VPD - spatial averages, annual mean, fire seasons only; (c) SPEI - spatial averages, annual mean, fire seasons only; (d) Heatwave frequency spatial

averages, annual mean, fire seasons only; (e) Total number of fires for each area per year; and (f) Burned area, spatial averages, annual mean, fire seasons only; (g) Spearman correlation between monthly average heat waves and fire count; (h) Information flow between monthly average heat waves and fire count.

Northern Region

In the northern region, the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) exhibits no clear trend (Fig. 1c), suggesting a relatively stable long-term balance between precipitation and evapotranspiration. Despite this stability, fire activity declined markedly, as evidenced by decreasing fire counts and burned area (Figs. 1e, 1f). The reduction in fire count indicates a lower frequency of ignition events—whether from natural causes such as lightning or human-induced activities—which may be attributed to improved fire management, shifts in land use, or changes in fuel availability. Concurrently, vapour pressure deficit (VPD) values, displayed a modest upward trend (Fig. 1b), indicating increased evaporative demand. However, the trends do not appear substantial, indicating that their corresponding influences may be not very significant as well. The combination of stable moisture conditions (SPEI) and only slight atmospheric drying (VPD) points towards a stronger influence of vegetation-driven, rather than atmosphere-driven, land–atmosphere regulation in these regions. This regulation limits the necessary conditions for wildfire ignition, resulting in reduced fire counts and burned area.

Southern Region

In the southern region, SPEI shows a modest upward trend (Fig. 1c), indicative of a slight improvement in the moisture balance and a potential reduction in drought severity. In contrast to the north, fire count remained relatively stable (Fig. 1e), even as the burned area continued to decline (Fig. 1f). This suggests that although ignitions are staying at the same level, individual fires are either less extensive or are being more effectively contained. Similar to the northern region, the southern region also experienced an upward trend in heatwave frequency (Fig. 1d), reinforcing the influence of intensifying extreme temperature events.

3.2 Discussion

While we initially hypothesized that the presence of heat waves during high fire-risk periods would increase the likelihood of fire activity, our analysis did not yield clear correlations or demonstrable causality between heatwave characteristics and fire events (Fig. 1g-h, and details in appendices A3 and A4). This finding contrasts with studies in other regions, such as southern Europe, where severe wildfires are closely linked to reduced precipitation and/or elevated air temperatures during the summer season (Santos et al., 2024). In these regions, negative trends in precipitation minus evapotranspiration (P-E) indicate intensifying drying, enhancing fire risks.

In tropical Africa, however, the influence of heatwaves appears more nuanced. Both regions studied experienced increasing heatwave frequency and atmospheric drying (VPD trends), but these climatic stresses did not directly translate into greater fire activity.

The contrasting trends between northern and southern regions can be partly attributed to differences in vegetation type, moisture availability, and human land use patterns. In the northern Sahelian zone, the gradual shift from grass-dominated savanna to woody shrubland also called 'woody encroachment' may have reduced fine fuel continuity, reducing the fire propagation potential (Stevens et al., 2017). Meanwhile in the southern region, widespread agricultural expansion and more intensive fire management efforts have likely suppressed the spatial extent of fires (Andela & van der Werf, 2014; Archibald, 2016).

Long-term observations indicate that many parts of tropical Africa, particularly across the Sahel and southern savannas, have experienced increasing precipitation over recent decades (Zubkova et al., 2019). Moreover, climatic feedbacks such as enhanced moisture retention due to vegetation adaptation could further decouple heatwave occurrence from fire spread (Veldman et al., 2015).

We assessed both the Spearman rank correlation and the Pearson linear correlation between heatwave frequency and fire count. While Spearman correlation (Fig. 1g) revealed widespread, albeit modest, positive relationships, Pearson correlation yielded weaker and more spatially constrained signals (Figs. A3 and A4). This suggests that the relationship between heatwaves and fire activity across tropical Africa is generally monotonic but not strictly linear. Nonetheless, the overall weak correlations observed across both methods underscore the limited direct coupling between heatwave events and fire activity in the study regions.

Limitations

The spatial resolution of the ERA5 data (0.25 degrees) may have smoothed out some local variations in temperature and moisture, potentially affecting the accuracy of our heatwave and drought assessments. See Figures A2 and A3.

The temporal scope of our dataset (2003-2019) may not capture the full range of variability in fire regimes and climate extremes.

The MODIS fire products are known to not detect fires with small spatial extent (Roteta, 2019) and we may be underestimating fire counts and burned area.

While Spearman and Pearson correlations were both assessed, it remains possible that more complex, nonlinear relationships exist between heatwave frequency and fire activity that were not fully captured by these correlation methods.

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